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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ROLE OF CHRISTIANITY TEACHERS (CT) AND THE COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT IN PONTIANAK CITY OF WEST KALIMANTAN, INDONESIA

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to find out the relationship between the role of Christianity Teachers (CT) and the community development in the context of empowering the tribe of Dayak in Pontianak city, west Kalimantan province in Indonesia. This research is a causal study through regression analysis. The population of this study is the elementary, secondary and high schools in Pontianak. There were 89 units of analysis used as the sample who were chosen randomly. Findings indicates that there is positive impact of the role of CT on the community development. This research suggests that a good education on the CT is essential in improving human resources, especially in the success of local government program, aiming to create social, economic, and human rights justices.

Keywords: The Role of Christianity Teachers/CT; Community Development.

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1. Introduction

Humans are God's creatures who have high dignity. They are equipped with the ability to distinguish between the right and wrong, the good and bad, the fair and unfair, etc. Thus, humans always try their best for themselves and want a fair treatment. To achieve those values, humans create patterns of thought and action that benefit themselves without harming others. Humans are seated in equality; their rights are respected without neglecting that humans as God's creations are obliged to carry out the mission from the God. Consequently, humans are seated in accordance with their dignity and in accordance with the provisions and abilities given by God. Only in this way will humans be treated properly and appropriately. This is called the concept of Indonesian humanity which can be a reference in peoples' attitudes, behavior and actions.

The forms of social injustice that occur to Christians appear in several ways, among others. First is the opportunity for Christians to be Civil Servants of teachers in public schools. Although, it has been stipulated in the 1945 of Indonesian Constitution that every citizen is given the same opportunity, protection and rights. No discrimination is reflected in the constitution including the opportunity to be a civil servant or government officers. Second is the distribution of teaching materials supporting the implementation of Christianity Teachers (CT). Moreover, there are some schools with inadequate facilities for learning process where the rooms are too small, narrow and close to the toilet. Third is the implementation of education and training for the development of Human Resources (HR) of CT in schools as well as pastors at Churches. There is an absence of structural positions in the section head of the Ministry of Religion in Pontianak City.

Fourth is lack of human resource development in the sense of further study in a higher education level. Due to limited scholarship programs for pursuing Master and Doctoral programs. Fifth is the distribution of honorarium for non-permanent of CT in public schools from elementary to high schools. Sixth is the right to establish a place of worship i.e. church. Many churches are still not recognized by the Pontianak city government. Based on data from the Christian Community Guidelines of the Ministry of Religion in Pontianak, there are nine churches that stand in permanent shophouses (Office Houses). The function of the existence of the communication forum for religious community established by the government is intended as a direction to help simplify requirements of establishing a place of worship. The fact is that the composition of CFRC members who are Christian-Catholic decreases in number. Seventh is social assistance (Social Aid) intended for the construction of houses of worship or churches is still lacking. It is proven by data from the Christian Community Guidance Office of the Ministry of Religion in Pontianak, where there are still three not permanent churches and twelve semi-permanent church buildings.

A CT is driven by an understanding of the implementation of the nature and function of the church as a whole in the community. However, it is realized that giving of CT in schools and local churches are not maximum. Therefore, there is the need of social justice which cannot be only a cliché where the real practice is not so. According to Franz Magniz Suseno in his book 'Political Ethics', the final implementation of social justice depends on the structure of economic, political, social, cultural, and ideological processes that exist in society, and policies in the hands of government (Franz, 1987). In Pontianak community, the Dayaknese is always connoted as Christians or Catholics. Furthermore, the voice of the Dayak tribe to defend equality of political rights is often connoted as the voices of socio-economic and political backwardness of the Christian side to defend their destiny at home (Muhrotien, 2012). The Dayak tribe, in general, adheres to Christianity, although there are some of Dayaknese believe in Islam and Buddhism. This occurs due to a process of social interaction among tribes, resulting in intermarriage between ethnic and religious groups (Florus, 1994). Nevertheless, it is suspected that there is a practice of discrimination, especially in the government. The hypothesis is that the situation occurs and clearly contains political power as one of the motives. The fact is that is when the government takes various policies without considering the rights of the minority. Obviously, it will be difficult to fight for because of many interests in the community. Often, there is a perception of distrust of Christians from the Dayak tribe against the government's commitment to equitable development in accordance to the mandate of the *Pancasila*, principle I and the 1945 Constitution which is set out in other positive laws including Regional Regulations.

During the last few years, *Pancasila*, which contains national cultural values and spirit for the life of the nation, seems to be forgotten. Consequently, there is a tendency of losing moral norms in national life and patriotic. Pancasila, which is mandated in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, not only contains national cultural values, but also becomes the foundation of national law, and is a manifestation of lofty ideals in all aspects of national life. In other words, the values of Pancasila must also be translated into moral norms, development norms, legal norms, and ethics of national life. In fact, Indonesian people have a strong formal foundation and clear guidelines for the future development of the aspired Indonesian society. The problem is how to actualize it into the real life in every citizen, so that this nation does not lose moral norms as the guidance of carrying out the movement and reform, overcoming multidimensional crises including the moral crisis which obstructs the nation in reaching its goals. Pancasila is also based on the axiom: "That man and the universe are God's creations in harmony" where it is essential to find the concepts, principles and values contained therein.

As a logical consequence of the axiom mentioned above, an acknowledgment occurs that the universe, including humans, is God's creation, and God has governed it with definite laws, and has provided everything necessary to maintain the continuity of its existence. The God has provided humans with certain competencies. Based on the background above, the researcher conducted an empirical study to discuss the main points of this issue, especially on: "The Relationship between the Role of Christianity Teachers (CT) on the Community Development in Pontianak City, West Kalimantan".

2. Research Methodology and Data Collection

The type of this research is a survey research through quantitative approaches. The intended survey research seeks to explain the causal relationship and hypothesis testing. Causal approach is an analysis of whether or not there is an influence between one variable and other variables. According to Masri Singarimbun in his book entitled, "Survey Research Methods", a survey research can be used for (1) exploratory, (2) descriptive, (3) explanatory and confirmatory, (4) evaluation, (5) predictions about events in the future, (6) operational research, and (7) the development of social indicators (Singarimbun & Effendi, 2002). Conceptually, in preparing a causal model for the role of the Christian Religious Teachers of Dayak Community Development in Pontianak City, the problem was on how determining variables and indicators in the model including independent and dependent variables. Sasmoko said that the sequence in compiling the model must be based on the correct theory or hypothesis (Singarimbun & Effendi, 2002). That is the theory derived from experts. It can also be based on hypotheses, the researcher builds a hypothetical paradigm according to the needs of what is happening in the field. Data collection techniques consisted of 2 types, namely a questionnaire to measure the influence of the role of Christianity Teachers (CT) on Dayak Community Development in Pontianak city of West Kalimantan Province. The content validation and construct validation were also obtained for this research. Sasmoko said that content validity pointed out to the extent to which the instrument reflects the desired content (Sasmoko, 2007).

Population of this research was public schools, in the level of junior and senior high schools in the City of Pontianak, West Kalimantan Province. Instrument of each variable was in the form of a questionnaire with questions or statements by using a measurement scale of five alternative

choices. The answer to the questionnaire was the perception of the respondents. The questionnaire was used as a data collection tool which was first tested on an analysis unit of 30 respondents with a view to knowing whether each item of the research variable was valid and each variable was reliable. The instrument testing was carried out as a standardization requirement so that it could be used as a data collection tool further. Validity testing was intended to find out whether the instruments made in the questionnaire could really measure and what will be measured. While the reliability calculation was intended to find out whether the instrument could be trusted to get the same results if they are measured at different times. Through testing the validity, it can be known which items are valid or acceptable which meet the requirements to be used as a measurement tool in this study, and which items are invalid. Items that do not meet the requirements were removed from the list of questions. Valid items were distributed again for data collection. By fulfilling the validity and reliability requirements of an instrument, the instrument could be used as a measurement tool for this research.

3. Results and Discussion

This research followed some activities in relation to data collection, analysis, discussion, and conclusion through measuring the role of CT to the Community Development. Description of data was presented as the result of processed raw data using descriptive statistical techniques that aim to provide an overview of the data distribution presented in several forms. They are: the form of frequency distribution, total score, average score price, standard deviation, mode, median, maximum score and minimum score which are accompanied by a histogram. The description of each data consists of the variable role of CT (X), and Community Development (Y). The calculation results of each variable are presented as follows:

Variable of the Role of CT (X):

- a) Basic Statistical Calculations
 - 1) The number of questions is 32,
 - 2) Number of valid questions is 29,
 - 3) The total score of items is 9915,
 - 4) The smallest value is 91.
 - 5) The biggest value is 131.
 - 6) Range of scores = Biggest value - smallest value (c - b) = 131 - 91 = 40,
 - 7) Average rating (mean) 111.40,
 - 8) Midpoint (median) 111,
 - 9) Mode (values that often appear) 119,
 - 10) Standard deviation 10,190
 - 11) Variants 103,8268
 - 12) Interval 6.

Table 1 is the frequency distribution table based on the acquisition of results:

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of the Role of Christianity Teachers (X)

No. of Sequence	Class Interval	Frequency				
		Down Limit	Top Limit	Absolute	Relative (%)	Cumulative (%)
1.	91-97	90.50	97,50	11	12.36	12.36
2.	98-104	97,50	104.50	12	13.48	25.84
3.	105-111	104.50	111.50	21	23.60	49.44
4.	112-118	111.50	118.50	23	25.84	75.28
5.	119-125	118.50	125.50	14	15.73	91.01
6.	126-132	125.50	132.50	8	8.99	100
TOTAL				89	100	

From the above Frequency Distribution table, the histogram can be depicted as follows:

Figure 1: Histogram of the Role of Christianity Teachers (X)

b) Community Development variable (Y)

Basic statistical calculations as followed:

- 1) The number of questions is 32,
- 2) Number of valid questions 28,
- 3) The total score of items is 9496,
- 4) The smallest value is 86.
- 5) The biggest value is 126.
- 6) Range of scores = Biggest value - smallest value (c - b) = 126 - 86 = 40,
- 7) Average value (mean) 106.70,
- 8) Middle value (median) 107,
- 9) Mode (values that often appear) 105,
- 10) Standard Deviation 10.9884,
- 11) Variance 120,6505,
- 12) Interval 6.

Table 2 shows the frequency distribution based on the acquisition of results:

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Community Development (Y)

No. of Sequence	Class Interval	Frequency				
		Down Limit	Top Limit	Absolute	Relative (%)	Cumulative (%)
1.	86-93	85.50	93.50	15	16.85	16.85
2.	94-100	93.50	100.50	10	11.24	28.09
3.	101-107	100.50	107.50	19	21.35	49.47
4.	108-114	107.50	114.50	24	26.97	76.44
5.	115-121	114.50	121.50	9	10,11	86.55
6.	122-128	111.50	128.50	12	13.48	100
Total				89	100	

Based on the above table of Community Development of Frequency Distribution (Y), the histogram can be pictured as follows:

Figure 2: Histogram of Variable Community Development (Y)

Furthermore, a summary of descriptive data calculations can be presented as follows:

Table 3: Summary of Results of Descriptive Data Calculations

No.	Statistics	X	Y
1.	Items are valid	29	28
2.	N	89	89
3.	lowest score	91	86
4.	Top scores	131	126
5.	Score range	40	40
6.	Mean	111.40	106.70
7.	median	111	107
8.	modus	119	105
9.	Standard Deviation	10.190	10.984
10.	variance	103.8168	120.6505
11.	long Class	6	6
12.	Total score	9915	9496

Analysis Requirements Test

As a follow-up analysis, regression is a process to systematically estimating what is most likely happens in the future based on what happens now so that errors can be corrected. Thus, testing requirements is a must, both for the sake of prediction and testing hypotheses. The requirements that have be met before conducting a regression analysis are: (a) Testing the estimated error normality ($Y - \hat{Y}$) from a simple regression; and (b) testing the significance and linearity of Y over X in the form of simple regression. From the requirements of the analysis, first, test the normality of the estimated error of regression with the assumption that the population is normally distributed. Next, the significance and linearity of Y over X is through testing a simple regression form using the analysis of variance (Anova).

Normality Test

Prior to testing the simple linear regression analysis, the researcher checked the data, whether the collected data has fulfilled the requirements, i.e. the data was obtained from a normally distributed population. Normality test estimated error Y over X, whether it has a normal distribution or not. The test conditions are: Ho is accepted if the estimated error ($Y - \hat{Y}$) is normally distributed and Ho is rejected when the estimated error ($Y - \hat{Y}$) is not normally distributed. The statistical hypothesis is:

Ho: ($Y - \hat{Y}$) is normally distributed, then

Ho: ($Y - \hat{Y}$) is not normally distributed

The normality error test is estimated to determine whether or not; the distribution of the sample was analyzed by using the Normality test using Liliefors or L, with the following test criteria:

Accept Ho if L arithmetic < L table,

Reject Ho if L count > L table

Based on the calculation results of the estimated error of normality test of the research variables obtained through using Test for Normality Error of Y and regression estimated for X, namely: $\hat{Y} = a + bX$. The results of calculating the estimated normality of the regression are that constant values (a) and slope values (b) can be searched. Regression equation calculation results was obtained at $\hat{Y} = 48.77 + 0.52 X$. From the calculation of the estimated error of regression obtained Lo results of 0.0663. The value of L table with respondents (n as many as 89 people) is at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ of 0.0939 (calculation of L table $n > 30$ at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ is $0.886 / \sqrt{89} = 0.886 : 9.434 = 0.0939$). Thus L count 0.663 is less from L table 0.0939 at the level $\alpha = 0.05$, then Ho is accepted. In conclusion, the estimated error in the regression equation $\hat{Y} = 48.77 + 0.52 X$ is normally distributed. By proving this calculation, all analysis have been implemented well then other calculation can be continued.

Testing of Significance and Linearity

Test of Significance

The regression employed as a way for decision making. For this reason, the hypothesis test regarding the significance and linearity of the regression form was carried out first. The hypothesis testing was conducted in order to determine whether the null hypothesis (Ho) submitted by the researcher is accepted or rejected at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis testing was in the form of regression analysis to determine the form of influence between variables. A simple regression analysis was used in the form of the compilation of the regression equations

accompanied by testing the significance of the regression and linearity testing of the regression form and the multiple regression analysis was also accompanied by significance testing. To determine the strength of influence between variables, correlation analysis was conducted. In this research, the correlation analysis and determination, multiple determination analysis, and multiple correlation were all accompanied by significance testing.

The hypothesis proposed in this study was the role of the CT has the direct positive effect on the community development. The meaning of the hypothesis is that the better the role of the CT, the better the development of the community. Simple regression analysis between the role of CT with the development of management in the society produces a direction of the regression coefficient "b" of 0.52, and a constant of "a" of 48.77, then the shape of the influence between the role of the CT and the community development was based on the calculation of the equation simple regression $\hat{Y} = 48.77 + 0.52 X$. To find out the significance of the simple regression equation, the F value test was performed, as follows:

Table 4: ANOVA Significance and Linearity of Simple Regression $\hat{Y} = 48.77 + 0.52 X$

Source variance	dk	JK	RJK	F count	Ftabel	
					$\alpha = 0.05$	$\alpha = 0.01$
Total	89	1023944	1023944			
The coefficient (a)	1	1,013,084.49	1,013,084.49	25.10 **	3.94	6,90
Regression (b / a)	1	2431.60	2431.60			
rest	87	8427.91	96.87			
tuna Matches	34	1607.15	47.27	0,37ns	1.60	1.94
error	53	6820.76	128.69			

Information:

** = very significant regression

ns (Non-Significant) = regression linear shape

Anova of calculation as the table above, it can be seen $F \text{ count} > F \text{ table}$ at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$, significant regression or significance level $\alpha = 0.01$, then a significant regression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F \text{ count} &= \frac{JK (\text{Reg})}{JK (S) / (n - 2)} \\
 &= \frac{2431.60}{96.87} \\
 &= 25.10
 \end{aligned}$$

In the list above table shows that the value of $F \text{ count} = 25.10$ while the $F \text{ table} = 3.94$ at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and $F \text{ table} = 6.90$ at the level of $\alpha = 0.01$. $F \text{ count}$ larger than $F \text{ table}$ can be stated that the regression equation is significant.

Linearity Regression Test

Furthermore, Anova calculation in the table above is if F arithmetic < F table at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ or 0.01 , then the linear regression is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{F count} &= \frac{\text{JK (TC)} / (k - 2)}{\text{JK (G)} / (n - k)} \\
 &= \frac{47.27}{128.69} \\
 &= 0.37
 \end{aligned}$$

The result of the calculation as in the table above shows that the value of F count is at 0.37, while the F table = 1.60 is at the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and F table = 1.94 at the level of $\alpha = 0.01$, because of the smaller F count of F table, the relationship of X3 and X1 is linear.

Obtaining the above test can be depicted at graph as follows:

Figure 3: Graph of Equation of Regression $\hat{Y} = 48.77 + 0.52 X$

Based on the table of the significance and linearity testings, it can be concluded that the regression equation which is $\hat{Y} = 48.77 + 0.52 X$, is significant and linear. The regression equation can provide an idea that the increase in one score of the role of CT will be followed by an increase in community development of 0.52 at a constant of 48.77. The results of the calculation of the strength of the relationship of the role of teachers of CT (X) to community development (Y) are shown by the correlation coefficient $r_{y1} = 0, 0.4689$. Furthermore, the significance of the correlation coefficient can be seen at the table below:

Table 5: Test the Significance of Correlation Coefficients The Role of CT (X) on the Community Development (Y)

n	Correlation Coefficient (ry1)	t	t table	
			$\alpha = 0.05$	$\alpha = 0.01$
89	.4689	4.953	1.658	2,358

The results of the calculation of the significance of the correlation coefficient test can be concluded that the correlation coefficient of the role of CT (X) to community development (Y) of 0.4689 is significant, it can be concluded that there is a positive direct effect on the role of CT in community development. This shows the better the role of the CT, the better the development of the community. The results of the determinant correlation coefficient, $ryx = (0.4689)^2 = 0.2199$. This means that a percentage of 21.99 percent of the community development variable (Y) can be expressed by the role of the CT (X).

Hypothesis Testing

Data for all variables were processed using the SPSS 16 program. The analysis was carried out after the calculation of significance and linearity to produce significant and linear results. Furthermore, the influence test was done using SPSS 16. The results of testing the hypothesis is an influence of the role of the CT on the development of the Community (Y) through the statistical hypothesis as follows:

Ho: $\beta: \leq 0$
 H1: $\beta: < 0$

SPSS 16 results are shown in the table below:

Table 6: Coefficients

Model	Coefficients unstandardized		standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	beta		
1 (Constant)	49 290	11 640		4,235	.000
role of Teachers	.515	.104	.469	4952	.000

Dependent Variable: Community Development

Analysis of the statistics shows that there is standardized coefficients at 0.469. To prove whether the acquisition of this value has an influence was through comparing the calculated t value with t table. Thus, if it is $t_{arithmetic} >$ from t table meaning that there is influence, but when if $t_{arithmetic} <$ from t table, meaning that there is no effect. Findings shows that the obtained t count is 4.952 with t table in the level of $\alpha = 0.05$ of 1.658 and $\alpha = 0.01$, amounting to 2.358. Thus, there is an influence of the role of Christian religious education on the community development.

The effect values of the test results are below:

Figure 9: hypothetical Empirical Research

X = Role of CT, Y = Community Development

4. Discussion

In an effort to improve the quality of education is the responsibility of all components of the nation. The leaders of the nation work together in order to have good quality of humans as mandated by the 1945 Constitution. Plurality of the Indonesian nation in terms of ethnicity, religion, and class is challenges in achieving goals. Moreover, the country is the type of the archipelago country

where all islands can not be separated from one another in the frame of the Unitary Republic of Indonesia. There cannot be compartmentalized in the development. This gap leads the researcher to conduct a research at the elementary and junior high schools in Pontianak city of West Kalimantan Province of Indonesia on Christian religious teachers. This research aims to find out how the role of CT as mobilizers students to contribute in realizing community development in the Pontianak city. Empirical findings provide a significant and linear role for CT in community development. There is significant results because some evidences such as $F_{count} = 25.10 >$ from $F_{table} 3.94$ at $\alpha = 0.05$ level and $F_{table} 6.90$ at $\alpha = 0.01$ level. The findings are also linear because several factors such as $F_{arithmetic} = 0.37 <$ from $F_{table} 1.60$ at $\alpha = 0.05$ level and $F_{table} = 1.94$ at $\alpha = 0.01$ level. The use of SPSS 16 could calculate the role of Christian religious education on community development of 0.469. The T-test was obtained at $4.962 >$ from $t_{table} 1.668$ at $\alpha = 0.05$ and 2.358 at $\alpha = 0.01$, then the path was significant. This shows the theory cited supporting the researcher in conceptualizing definitions, operational definitions and instruments. The percentage of relationships disclosed by community development on the role of CT is by correlation coefficient at $(0.4689)^2 = 0.2199$ or at 21.99%. This percentage shows that the CT increases knowledge, values, norms as guidance in acting and behaving.

5. Conclusion

This research has explained trends in the influence of the role of CT (Variable X) on the community development with regard to economic justice, political justice, social justice and human rights justice in the Dayak Tribes of Pontianak, West Kalimantan (Variable Y). The first hypothesis of this research is accepted through some indicators of the variable of the role of CT with perceptions of justice expectations in the Dayak tribe, Pontianak, West Kalimantan. First is that the trend in economic democratic justice indicators (X1) is at the fair category. Second is that the trend on the political democratic justice (X2) is at the less fair category. Third is that the trend in social democratic justice indicators (X3) is at less fair category. Fourth is that the trend in human rights justice indicators (X4) is at less fair category. CT's perceptions of the expectations of economic, politics, social and human rights in the Dayak tribes of Pontianak, West Kalimantan (Y) are indicators of political democratic justice (X2) so that the second hypothesis is proven. The dominant background which influences the role of CT teachers on community development in economic, politics, social and human rights in the Dayak tribes of Pontianak - West Kalimantan (Y), is at the age background category so the third hypothesis is not proven/accepted.

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